

ACER
Albanian Center for Economic Research

Albanian Socio-Economic Review (ASER)

PRINT ISSN: 2222-5846

ONLINE ISSN: 2312-5349, Volume 1,

Issue 3, 2024

WASTE MANAGEMENT AND MUNICIPALITY REVENUE: A CASE STUDY OF VLORA MUNICIPALITY

Amali ÇIPI, Zamira SINAJ

University of Vlora “Ismail Qemali, Sheshi Pavarësia, 9401 Vlorë, Albania,
amalia.cipi@univlora.edu.al, zamira.sinaj@univlora.edu.al

ABSTRACT

With the rapid growth of population, urbanization, and economic development, particularly in developing nations, waste generation is escalating significantly. Conventional waste disposal methods contribute to numerous issues, including air pollution, groundwater and soil contamination, and greenhouse gas emissions, which pose serious threats to community infrastructure and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, urban waste management is a pressing issue for local authorities, requiring significant investments to address the closure of dumping sites that are typically unauthorized and non-compliant with local plans, as well as to establish a landfill for urban waste management. However, constructing a landfill demands substantial funding, which is often beyond the financial capacity of local governments. In this article we focus on the Municipality of Vlora, one of the largest municipalities in the country, strategically positioned to attract increased investments in infrastructure and services to support tourism development. The central-local government collaboration being implemented in the Municipality of Vlora, along with the municipality's efforts to attract investments, will be addressed through analyses, graphs, and fundamental questions aimed at identifying and addressing the problem related with waste management.

KEYWORDS: waste management, local government, Integrated management, Urban waste, Population growth, Development

1. INTRODUCTION

Human activities generate waste, which in the 21st century has become a burden for the entire planet, the environment, ecosystems, and humanity. Furthermore, the rapid increase in urban populations in recent years has made waste management a significant challenge for every city. The situation is equally alarming in administrative units (former municipalities), where waste is often dumped in unsafe areas, typically near riverbanks or along roadsides. The situation is further exacerbated by the fact that hazardous waste from the industrial sector is disposed of in the same locations as urban waste and is treated in the same manner. In most cases, waste is either burned or left to decompose, turning these areas into breeding grounds for infection.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND LEGAL BACKGROUND IN WASTE MANAGEMENT

Urban waste management represents the core and most challenging aspect of cleaning services, becoming one of the most pressing issues for local government authorities in Albania (Kodra & Milios, 2013)¹. Population growth, tourism development, business expansion (such as restaurants, markets, and bars), economic growth, and improved living standards have increased consumption rates and, consequently, the

¹ Kodra & Milios, 2013

scale and volume of urban waste generation. Inadequate waste management has turned waste into a source of environmental pollution and health issues.

In Albania, only a small fraction of waste is recycled, a limited amount is buried, and the majority is disposed of in designated landfills that fail to meet the necessary engineering standards for environmental protection and are frequently subject to fires. The burning of urban waste or its dumping along riverbanks and streams has become the most severe form of environmental pollution, resulting in high levels of air pollution while also contaminating soil and groundwater near these landfills (Alcani & Dorri, 2013)².

Following this, after the 2000s, a series of laws and bylaws were adopted to regulate waste management issues, categorize waste, and develop a waste catalog aligned with the European Community's Directives (Commission Decision 2014/955/EU and Council Directive 2008/98/EC). These efforts were complemented by various strategies in their respective fields. Key legislative and regulatory acts include Law No. 10463, dated 22.09.2011, "On Integrated Waste Management," Law No. 10431, dated 09.06.2011, "On Environmental Protection," Decision of the Council of Ministers (DCM) No. 452, dated 11.07.2012, "On Waste Landfills," and DCM No. 99, dated 18.02.2005, "On the Approval of the Albanian Waste Classification Catalog," among others. The regulations established through these laws laid the foundation for organizing public cleaning services and urban waste management, as well as revenue collection mechanisms to cover associated costs. These frameworks have since been consolidated and further refined with the adoption of new legislation, such as Law No. 9632, dated 30.10.2006, "On the Local Tax System," Law No. 139/2015, dated 17.12.2015, "On Local Self-Government," and specific laws governing waste and its classification (e.g., DCM No. 99, dated 18.02.2005, "On the Approval of the Albanian Waste Classification Catalog").

In this sense, waste management, encompassing the collection, transportation, disposal, and treatment of urban waste (Law 139/2015 "On Local Self-Government," Article 23, Paragraph 10), is a direct responsibility of Local Government Units (LGUs). Following this, since LGUs are responsible for managing urban waste, they are tasked with determining landfill sites within their jurisdictions (Law 139/2015 "On Local Self-Government," Article 23, Paragraph 10) and setting the service fee for waste management (Law 139/2015 "On Local Self-Government," Article 9, Paragraph C/b).

In Albania, the responsibilities for managing urban waste are divided at the national, regional, and local levels. Law no. 10463/2011 "On Integrated Waste Management" and Law no. 156/2013 "On Amendments to Law no. 10463/2011" are the primary legal acts aimed at protecting the environment and human health, ensuring proper environmental management of waste. The main objectives of these laws are:

1. *Prevention and minimization of waste* or reducing the negative impacts of integrated waste management.
2. *Improvement of the efficiency of waste usage.*
3. *Reduction of the overall negative impacts from the use of resources.*

The law also sets out the institutional structures and responsibilities in the field of waste management, including the Ministry of Tourism and Environment (MTM) and its subordinate agencies, as well as the Ministry of Infrastructure and Energy (MIE), which is the Albanian partner in the preparation of the National Waste Management Investment Plan. This law also envisions the development of national, regional, and local waste management plans.

On the other hand, Law no. 139/2015 "On Local Self-Government" defines the responsibilities and authority of Local Government Units (LGUs) in managing waste in Albania. According to this law, waste collection, transport, disposal, and treatment are the responsibility of the municipalities. Municipalities have the right and responsibility to manage waste services in accordance with their local conditions and to collaborate with other municipalities to set service tariffs and revenue collection mechanisms. They are also responsible for the construction and management of waste treatment facilities (Decentralization and Local Development Program, 2012)³.

² Alcani & Dorri, 2013

³ Decentralization and Local Development Program, 2012

However, local government units are very weak and lack the financial capacity, organizational structure, and professional expertise to cope with the challenges of managing urban waste. They often do not have the mandate to regulate this sector, and delays in adapting regulations occur due to the rapid evolution of the sector, creating barriers for public institutions to provide adequate services.

Another problem is that contracts between municipalities and private companies for waste services are often of poor quality, with issues such as unclear role and responsibility definitions and inadequate measures to minimize risks. Furthermore, many municipalities tend to contract more services than they can afford financially.

Improving waste management requires investments and expertise that the public sector is often unable to provide. Involvement of the private sector in urban waste management could lead to a shift in the role of public institutions from service providers to regulatory bodies. However, this transition is not always successful, particularly in developing countries, where public institutions often fail to ensure a smooth and sustainable transfer to the private sector. The lack of monitoring and control systems, as well as the relevant knowledge at both central and local levels, remains a significant challenge.

3. CURRENT SITUATION OF WASTE MANAGEMENT IN VLORA MUNICIPALITY

The recommendations given by state institutions operating in the environmental field or foreign bodies that have conducted various monitoring activities in the Municipality of Vlorë include suggestions for waste disposal in the Soda Forest and Dukat areas, as well as in the villages of Administrative Units that dispose of urban waste mainly in rivers, streams, canals, or near settlements (KfW Entwicklungsbank, 2018)⁴.

The description of the current situation in the Municipality of Vlorë presents a scenario where in urban areas, cleaning services are performed with all the issues they carry, while in rural areas the quality of cleaning services is much lower. However, what is common to both is the management of waste, where in both cases the situation is alarming. This has led to increased efforts by the Municipality of Vlorë and the Albanian government to solve the situation and secure various donations. The biggest step has been finding funds for the construction of the Shërishta Landfill.

In the negotiation phase for securing donors, the interested institutions, in collaboration with specialists from the Municipality of Vlorë and based on the current situation, developed the Integrated Waste Management System for the Vlorë Region – Final Report of the Feasibility Study (2015). This study provides a detailed description of the current waste situation in Vlorë, from which we will break down some essential parts for our analysis, as the other sections are entirely technical and go beyond the scope of this thesis. These sections of the study assist in the subsequent chapters on cost analysis and answering other questions related to these issues, which we raised in section 2.4 “Basic Questions.”

Based on the Integrated Waste Management System for the Vlorë Region – Final Report of the Feasibility Study (2015), due to the size and expected environmental impact, the landfills in the project area can be categorized into three different categories (See Annex, Table 1):

- **Category A**, which includes the Panaja village disposal site (AU Center), needs to be excavated and transported to the new sanitary landfill.
- **Category B** includes the Shushica (NjSh Shushica) and Mifol & Trevllazër (Nj. Novoselë) disposal sites, with moderate environmental impact. These landfills should be rehabilitated on-site. The following measures are recommended:
 1. Compacting waste and modeling the landfill surface
 2. Stabilization layer/gas drainage
 3. Mineral clay layer
 4. Water drainage layer
 5. Vegetative soil layer
 6. Installation of a gas collection system (drained gas or "open gas shaft") for controlled landfill discharge.

⁴ KfW Entwicklungsbank, 2018

- **Category C** includes the landfills of Vlorë and Orikum, where it has been concluded that the waste disposal sites in the Soda Forest and Dukat fields should be urgently closed, accompanied by rehabilitation measures according to EU Directive 99/33/EC. Rehabilitation works include filling and covering the surface, surface isolation, gas drainage, and vegetation layers.

In conclusion, it can be said that the Municipality of Vlorë, as a municipality with clear objectives for tourism development, playing a key role in the economy of the Vlorë region, particularly in Vlorë and Orikum, is mainly characterized by the quality of these services. The cleanliness of the streets in Vlorë (center), beaches, and other tourist areas is essential. The municipality should start taking immediate actions to implement the environmental provisions that have come into force in recent years, as well as prepare the Local Urban Waste Management Plan. However, this service has faced its own problems due to demographic growth, territorial expansion, poor road conditions, low awareness about waste disposal, garbage dumping, and the spread of construction debris, as well as illegal dumping.

4. METHODOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The selection of this topic aimed to analyze and discuss one of the biggest problems of local government, which is the realization of cleaning services, with a special focus on the management of urban waste generated by the community within the territorial area it serves, as well as municipality revenue from providing this service.

Based on the current legislation (Law 139/2015 "On Local Government" and Law No. 9632, dated 30.10.2006 "On the Local Tax System"), the local self-government units are financed by revenue generated from taxes, tariffs, and other local income, from funds transferred from the central government, and funds directly received from the distribution of national taxes, local borrowing, donations, and other sources provided by law. Based on the total of these revenues, local authorities prepare their budgets, planning expenses and costs for a fiscal year, which also include the costs for providing cleaning services.

Revenue from their sources is regulated by the law "On the Local Tax System," which determines the taxes and tariffs set by local government units for their community, their levels, and the collection procedures. The revenues from "their sources" include the obligation paid by residents or businesses, as beneficiaries of cleaning and waste management services, which under legal provisions are classified as tariffs. In daily practice, they are titled as "cleaning fees" or "family tariffs," for which the municipal council decides on types, levels, basic rules for their administration and collection, as well as determines whether these fees will be collected by the municipal structures themselves or by a tax agent.

The implementation of the cleaning service has a relatively large weight, usually accounting for about 20-30% of the budget, or about 50-60% of expenses. Below, these figures will be analyzed in detail under the focus of the research questions we have posed (2.4 Basic Questions), which are related to the revenue aspect, as follows: *What are the fees currently paid by the community, and how are these fees collected? (This question includes several sub-questions with a focus on: What is the annual revenue collected from these fees? Are costs covered by these revenues? What solutions have been provided by the Municipality of Vlorë in cases where expenses are not covered?) Should the price of the cleaning service be increased? How will this increase be implemented: gradually or immediately?*

The Municipality of Vlorë has approved the decision for the fiscal package to be implemented in 2020, creating the conditions for the implementation of a fiscal policy to balance expenditures with revenues for cleaning services and urban waste management. The development of this fiscal policy was based on an analysis of the planning and realization of revenues over the past three years and covering costs (QKD No. 109, dated 27.11.2019). Specifically, based on the table below (Table 31), it is noted that in the years 2017, 2018, and 2019, the Municipality of Vlorë planned that through the collection of the cleaning fee from households and businesses, approximately 41.35%, 41.85%, and 42.52% of the value of the cleaning contract would be covered, respectively (Municipality of Vlorë: Budget, 2019).

The description provided presents an analysis of the actual revenue collection from the waste management fee in the Municipality of Vlora for the years 2017, 2018, and 2019. The analysis shows that the actual revenue collection is much lower than initially planned, although there is an increasing trend over these three years. This growth trend is described as approximately 5% (from 31.82% in 2017 to 36.88% in 2019).

However, only about 1/3 of the cost of the waste management service is covered by the waste management fee, while the remaining 68-63% is covered by other municipal revenues. This information suggests that the Municipality of Vlora covered more than 50% of the cost of the waste management service from other revenues before 2017, which may have negatively impacted the ability to use these revenues for investments or other community services. In this context, it is crucial for the municipality to implement a fiscal policy aimed at increasing the collection of revenue from the waste management fee and ensuring full coverage of the service costs. In conclusion, the Municipality of Vlora has carried out a monitoring of the waste management fee and linked this process to the processing of urban waste in landfills, a step aimed at improving the efficiency of revenue collection and waste management service delivery.

	Janar	Shkurt	Mars	Prill	Maj	Qershor	Korrik	Gusht	Shtator	Tetor	Nentor	Dhjetor
Nr. Diteve	31	28	31	30	31	30	31	31	30	31	30	31
Shperdarja e trafikut te turisteve						15%	35%	35%	15%			
Shperdarja e sasise te mbetjeve						389,9	909,7	909,7	389,9			
Mbetje shtese (per dite)						13	29,34	29,34	13			
Nr. I banoreve (per nate)						241 921	564 482	564 482	241 921			
Shperdarja e popullsise	70%	75%	80%	85%	100%	130%	155%	155%	130%	90%	80%	70%
Popullsia per cdo muaj	109 110	116 904	124 698	132 491	155 872	202 634	241 602	241 602	202 634	140 285	124 698	109 110
Sasia e mbetjeve per dite	98	105	112	119	140	182	217	217	182	126	112	98
Sasia e mbetjeve per dite (perfshire mbetjet nga turistet)	98	105	112	119	140	195	247	247	195	126	112	98

Table 1: Daily amount of waste in the 1-year period

5. CONCLUSIONS

In drawing the conclusions, it was simpler because they are in themselves the request of the community and belong to the competences implemented by the local government bodies. The conclusions we drew are as follows:

- Increasing the performance of the cleaning service. This should materialize in the daily removal of urban waste, such as sweeping and periodic washing of squares, sidewalks or streets. The performance of these services has a direct impact on increasing the quality of life, but also on improving the environment.
- The construction of the landfill will significantly improve the problem of urban waste processing, since the current landfills used in the city of Vlora and Orikum lack construction or operational measures to reduce emissions/protect the environment, thus having negative impacts on the population, flora and fauna, land, water, air and climate.
- The increase in the collection of the cleaning fee is a dynamic process, which forces the Municipality to be constantly careful in finding forms and ways for their payment by entities benefiting from the cleaning service.

References

1. "Marrëveshja: Shërbimi i pastrimit, Bashkia Vlorë", Bashkia Vlorë – "DUKA" sh.p., 2018.
2. "Marrëveshja: Shërbimi i pastrimit, në qytetin e Vlorës", Bashkia Vlorë – "DUKA" Sh.P., 25.11.2019, Nr.10224.
3. "Marrëveshja: Shërbimi i pastrimit në Njësinë Administrative Orikum", Bashkia Vlorë – "Baitel" sh.p., 06.12.2018, nr.10516.
4. "Marrëveshja: Shërbimi i pastrimit në Njësinë Administrative Orikum", Bashkia Vlorë – "Baitel" sh.p., 25.11.2019, Nr.10225.
5. "Marrëveshja: Kryerja e Shërbimit të Pastrimit në Bashkinë Orikum", Bashkia Orikum – "Baitel" Sh.p.k., 16 tetor 2013.
6. Alcani, M., & Dorri, A. (2013). Problemet që lidhen me situatën aktuale të mbetjeve të ngutar. *Revista Ndërkombëtare e Ekosistemeve dhe Shkencave Ekologjike (IJEES)*. Fjalori i Kembrixhit në internet. (2020). Marrë nga Cambridge University Press: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/waste>

7. Direktiva e Këshillit 1999/31/EC e datës 26 Prill 1999 mbi landfillin e mbetjeve. (1999). *Gazeta Zyrtare e Bashkimit Evropian*, L182. Marrë nga <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:182:TOC>
 8. Direktiva e Këshillit 1999/33/KE e datës 10 maj 1999 që amendon Direktivën e Këshillit 67/548/EEC në lidhje me etiketimin e disa substancave të rrezikshme në Austri dhe Suedi. (1999). *Gazeta Zyrtare e Bashkimit Evropian*, L 199. Marrë nga <https://eurlex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:31999L0033&qid=1587390019195&from=EN>
 9. Direktiva e Këshillit 2008/98/EC e datës 19 nëntor 2008 mbi mbetjet dhe shfuqizimin e disa direktivave. (2008). *Gazeta Zyrtare e Bashkimit Evropian*, L312, 3 – 30. Marrë nga <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098&from=EN>
 10. Vendimi i Komisionit 2014/955/BE i datës 18 dhjetor 2014 që ndryshon Vendimin 2000/532/EC për listën e mbetjeve në përputhje me Direktivën 2008/98/EC të Parlamentit Evropian dhe të Këshillit. (2014). *Gazeta Zyrtare e Bashkimit Evropian*, L 370/44. CELEX Nr.: 32008L0098. Marrë nga <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0955&from=EN>
- Programi i Decentralizimit dhe Zhvillimit Lokal. (2012). Planifikimi Lokal i Menaxhimit të Mbetjeve. Shkodër: HELVETAS Swiss Intercooperation Albania.
- Vendim “Për Prokurimin e Shërbimit të Pastrimit Publik dhe Grumbullimit të Mbetjeve”, Këshilli i Ministrave (Shqipëri), Nr. 319. (06 21, 1994). Marrë nga <https://qbz.gov.al/share/I7Z28-rSTMGoEdDny8KYIQ>